

**Study of Dissociation Constants of Stobbe
Condensation and Cyclisation Products**

SABA JABBAR and GEETA GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science,
Nagpur-440 001

*Manuscript received 10 April 1990, revised 10 October 1990,
accepted 23 November 1990*

IN the course of studies of fulgides for their photochemical properties¹, studies of their Friedel-Crafts cyclised products², products obtained from cyclisation of the diacids (obtained from the hydrolysis of anhydrides) with various cyclisation reagents³, and the Stobbe reaction products⁴ were studied for their dissociation constants.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The pH-titrations were carried out on a ELICO LI 10T pH-meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following sets of solutions, each of initial volume 40 ml and ionic strength $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) were prepared and pH-metrically titrated with a standard solution of $0.5 M$ NaOH : (i) 2 ml of $0.1 M$ HClO_4 + 4 ml of $1 M$ NaClO_4 + 4 ml of H_2O + 30 ml ethanol, and (ii) 2 ml of $0.1 M$ HClO_4 + 4 ml of $1 M$ NaClO_4 + 4 ml of H_2O + 10 ml of experimental compound + 20 ml of ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Dissociation constants of the experimental compounds were evaluated (Table 1) by Irving and Rossotti⁶ method. The pK_a values for acid-esters (1d) and pK_{a1} value of diacids² (1a, 1b, 1e, 1f and 1g)

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANT VALUES OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}	Compd. no.	pK_{a1}	pK_{a2}
1a	5.6	9.0	2e	6.24	—
1b	5.55	9.10	2f	4.81	8.53
1c	4.15	8.27	2g	5.87	7.26
1d	5.89	—	2h	5.50	7.80
1e	5.45	9.50	2i	4.93	7.97
1f	5.65	9.50	2j	6.12	7.78
1g	5.63	9.50		pK	
2a	6.33	—	4a	7.05	
2b	7.65	—	4b	8.36	
2c	6.93	—	4c	8.62	
2d	6.33	—	4d	7.12	

1

- 1a; $R^1 = \text{Ph}$, $R^2 = R^3 = \text{H}$
 1b; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ (β -OMe), $R^3 = \text{H}$
 1c; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Ph}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 1d; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Ph}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 1e; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_{10}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 1f; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{PhMe}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 1g; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Me}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$

2

- 2a; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_{10}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 2b; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_8$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 2c; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{PhMe}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 2d; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Me}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 2e; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Ph}$, $R^3 = \text{Me}$
 2f; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_{10}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 2g; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_8$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 2h; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{PhMe}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 2i; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Me}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$
 2j; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Ph}$, $R^3 = \text{H}$

3

4

- a; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_{10}$
 b; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{cyclo-C}_6\text{H}_8$
 c; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{PhMe}$
 d; $R^1 = R^2 = \text{Me}$

are constant and a fall in pK_{a1} of 1c must be due to the influence of phenyl over the carboxyl group which fall on the same side of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ (which is elsewhere absent).

The acid esters (2a–e) show the pK_a values in the range 6.2–7.6 and a decrease in acidity in case of these acid esters is apparent when compared with pK_a values of acid-esters (3) which fall in range 3.6–5.0⁶. The fall in acidity of the former acid esters could be attributed to the influence of the electronegative π cloud of the phenyl group over carboxyl present on the same side of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ double bond which is absent in the latter molecules. In diacids (2f–j), pK_{a1} values are more or less constant except in diacid 2j where fall in acidity could be again due to the influence of phenyl group as in acid-esters (2a–2e) above. The other carboxyl group is always under the influence of a phenyl substituent, therefore, pK_{a2} value is always higher and more or less constant (7.2–8.5).

The cyclised products (4a–d) show relatively constant pK_a values (7.2–8.5) where the carboxyl group could be imagined under the influence of the electronegative carbonyl function.

References

- G. H. BROWN, "Techniques of Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1971, Vol. III, p. 595.
- S. BANERJEE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **15**, 487.
- S. BANERJEE and G. BAGAVANT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **55**, 68; S. BANERJEE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 968.
- K. R. RAO and G. BAGAVANT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 859; S. BANERJEE and G. BAGAVANT, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 846; S. BANERJEE and G. BAGAVANT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 925; V. PATANKAR and S. BANERJEE, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 471.
- H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2910.
- S. BANERJEE and G. BAGAVANT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 362.